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Full Length Article

Damage kinetics in high-temperature irradiated Ni crystals

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ABSTRACT

High-temperature (~800 K) ion irradiation with 380 keV Ar ions was used to modify the surface of Ni single crystals in order to generate radiation defects and mimic the effect of neutrons avoiding sample activation. The modified 800 nm thick layer was analyzed regarding structural and mechanical properties utilizing a combination of experimental and simulation techniques. The ion implantation fluence ranged from $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ up to $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which corresponds to values of displacements per atom from 0.25 to 25, respectively. The structural characterization was performed by Rutherford Spectroscopy in Channeling mode (RBS/C) associated with scanning (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The experimental results were supported by Monte Carlo (McChasy) and Molecular Dynamics (MD-LAMMPS) simulations. The simulations performed using the second generation of the McChasy code show that the influence of bubbles formed inside the material is not negligible and affects the quantitative analysis of defects in the simulated spectra. A second step in damage kinetics was revealed for the highest dose (i.e., 25 dpa) as a consequence of the entanglement of dislocations and agglomeration of noble gas bubbles, which was confirmed by TEM analysis. Moreover, nanomechanical results confirm that Ar bubbles deteriorate mechanical properties such as hardness.

1. Introduction

One of the major challenges that have recently faced engineers and material scientists is studies of materials that can be used for high-temperature (HT) applications, e.g., in new generations of nuclear power plants. However, these materials must meet a number of essential criteria such as resistance to harsh environmental conditions, especially high temperatures, corrosive environments, and radiation. Therefore, in order to understand the influence of the above-mentioned factors, it is critical to examine the radiation effects, defect creation, and configuration and to understand the material's behavior at elevated temperatures.

Irradiation-induced degradation, e.g., swelling and hardening, is influenced by many factors related to material design and manufacturing processes, including major elements, solute additions, grain boundaries, or precipitates [1]. In addition, among the factors that influence the formation of radiation damage (e.g., particle energy, dose,

and dose rate), irradiation temperature can significantly influence the formation, migration, and evolution of defects [2]. Single crystals are good candidates to meet these requirements, due to the absence of grain boundaries, which gives a decrease in yield strength and the amount of creep, which is critical for high-temperature applications. Moreover, recent studies have shown, that this group of materials is characterized by high radiation tolerance and extraordinary mechanical properties [1,3–5]. E. Levo *et al.* [6] investigated temperature effect by means of simulations of implanted Ni and Ni-based EAMC-alloys at temperatures varying from 138 to 800 K. They have demonstrated that, with an increased temperature, the saturation level of accumulated point defects is lowered. Pure Ni has about twice the difference between the highest and lowest saturation temperatures, while alloys have a difference of a factor three. They also reported that the amount of interstitial-type clusters smaller than 20 nm is reduced as a function of temperature, opposite to the larger clusters. In the case of vacancy type clusters, the sizes are increasing with the temperature. In turn, Z. Fan *et al.* [2] made

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analysis of pure Ni and NiFe irradiated at temperatures varying from 150 to 500 K. They found that post-irradiation annealing at 500 K causes defect evolution and its effect is different compare to 150 K and 300 K. Annealing at 150 K causes defect migration to shallower depth. Moreover, the onset temperature for vacancy cluster dissociation has been found to be between 500 K and 700 K. Shi *et al.* [7] demonstrated that the size of the defects increase as a function of dose for in-situ ion irradiation using Kr ions that were implanted at 773 K in Ni and Ni-based alloys. In our previous work [8], we studied effects of 500 keV Ar and 550 keV Si in-situ irradiations with a fluences ranging from 2×10^{13} up to 1×10^{16} cm⁻² on pure Ni crystal and two equiatomic NiFe and NiFeCoCr alloys. The samples were irradiated at 16 K and room temperature (RT, i.e., ~300 K). We found that in the case of RT, the damage level measured for complex alloys at the highest irradiation fluence of 2×10^{15} cm⁻² (~3 dpa) was higher than that obtained for pure nickel samples and suggesting two-step damage accumulation process with a defect transformation taking place at the fluence of about 1.5×10^{15} cm⁻². Moreover, with increasing degree of chemical complexity and high solid-solution strengthening effects from Ni to NiFe and to NiFeCoCr, the enhanced lattice stiffness resists to randomization of atomic configurations and inhibits the growth of extended defects.

Despite such a wide characteristic, the structural and mechanical stability of these materials at elevated temperatures requires thorough understanding. Therefore, in this work, monocrystalline Ni structures implanted at 800 K with 380 keV Ar ions were used as the case study to analyze the formation of defects upon ion bombardment.

For the structural analysis of radiation-induced defects we utilized the Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry in channeling mode (RBS/C) combined with transmission (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The experimental techniques are accompanied by Monte Carlo (MC) and Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations. The MC

simulations were performed using two generations of McChasy codes [9,10] and Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) [11].

The studies of defect formation that pay attention to the evolution of dislocations and dislocation loops formed in Ni-based alloys seem to be very important [12], mainly because of their potential applications for the power generation sector [8,13,14]. In addition, the purpose of this study was to test the latest version of the McChasy-2 program, in which we added the ability to interpret gas bubbles in the material and examine their influence on the obtained RBS/C spectra.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

The Ni single crystal samples (1×1 cm²) were manufactured by MaTeck GmbH company. However, low crystallinity of the samples was revealed by preliminary SEM and RBS/C measurements (cf. Fig. 1(a) and (d)). An unexpectedly high channeling spectrum recorded for the pristine sample is the evidence of the presence of defects probably due to the method of sample manufacturing and the mechanical polishing (MP) used. For this reason, the samples were additionally pretreated in two ways before the originally planned modification by ion implantation. The reference sample was electro-polished (EP) using Struers LectroPol with 60% Perchloric acid electrolyte to reduce stress generated by MP. The electro-polishing time was set to 40 s, the electric potential to 30 V, and the temperature to 5 °C. The remaining samples were treated with a high-voltage electron beam gun (EG), which allows the generation of low-energy, high-current electron beams (LEHCEB) of a large diameter of ~10 cm. The major LEHCEB parameters are as follows: electron energy up to 30 keV, pulse duration of 2.5 μs, and energy density from 1 to 5 Jcm⁻². The parameters of the beam were chosen carefully to deposit

Fig. 1. SEM images captured before (a) and after (b) EG and (c) EP treatment as well as (d) RBS/C results obtained for pristine material before and after sample preparation (MP – mechanical polishing, EG – electron gun, EP – electro-polishing). Also shown in (d) is the aligned, pristine spectrum (orange solid line) as predicted by MC simulations in McChasy code (pristine MC sim.). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

enough energy per cm^2 (between 4 and 5 Jcm^{-2}) to allow recrystallization of the surface of the investigated material. The details regarding the method can be found elsewhere [15,16].

Fig. 1(a), (b), and (c) show the comparison of SEM images collected before and after the EG and EP treatment. Fig. 1(d) also shows RBS/C spectra of the pristine material prepared using both preparation techniques. From the comparison of the SEM pictures, one can see that all the visible scratches created by MP were removed. However, new structures, noticeable on the surface, appear after treating the sample with the electron gun. The observed craters are the natural elements of the surface microstructure of materials melted using electron [17], ion [18], plasma [19], or laser beams [20]. The authors of Ref. [17] suggest that the most probable mechanisms of crater formation during electron annealing are selective melting and subsequent erosion of individual surface areas due to differences in the melting temperature of phase components. Although the electron annealed surface of the single crystal is not ideal do not affect the channeling spectra, as can be seen in Fig. 1(d).

The minimum yield χ_{\min} of the RBS/C spectra, i.e., (aligned yield)/(random yield) calculated for the energy at 1400 keV decreased after using EG or EP methodology of sample preparation from 44% (MP) to 5% (EG and EP). It means that the quality of the material was significantly improved. The resulting quality is close to the perfect, undamaged one. For comparison, the simulation of the pristine material using only Ni thermal vibrations with the amplitude of their Gaussian distribution [21] and no structural defects was performed (orange solid line in Fig. 1(d)). The higher dechanneling intensities visible in lower energy range for EG and EP compared to the perfect one suggest that even in the pristine materials some defects remain.

2.2. Experimental techniques

The surface microstructure of the samples before the ion implantation was examined with the use of a Zeiss EVO® (Oberkochen, Germany) MA10 scanning electron microscope. The measurements were performed using the secondary electron detector.

The samples were ion-bombarded at Laboratório de Aceleradores e Tecnologias da Radiação (LATR) [22] at HT (~800 K) with 380 keV Ar^+ ions with a tilt of $\sim 7^\circ$ off the normal (100) direction to avoid channeled implantation. The implantation parameters were selected carefully to avoid interference between the surface and the conceivable damage peak (indicating point defects and small defect clusters) as well as to minimize ambiguities due to the straggling and dispersion of the probing ion beam that could arise if the damage peak was created in deeper region upon high energy implantation. Moreover, the chosen implantation temperature, 800 K, is assumed to be the main steam temperature obtained during High Temperature Gas Cooled Reactor (HTGR) operation [23,24]. The ion fluence ranged from $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which corresponds to values of displacements per atom (dpa) from 0.25 to 25, respectively. The dpa corresponds to low and moderate damage levels (1–50 dpa). These values are the displacement damage dose regimes for structural materials that are used in current Gen II fission reactors, Very High Temperature and High Temperature Gas Cooled Reactor (VHTR/HTGR), Super Critical Water Reactor (SCWR) and ITER fusion reactor [25–27].

RBS/C random and aligned energy spectra were recorded using a 2.0 MeV He^+ ion beam and a silicon pin-diode detector located at a 140° backscattering angle.

Suitable electron transparent lamellae were prepared from the area of interest of the samples via FIB/SEM for TEM microstructural studies. A lift-out procedure was utilized in FIB (Ga^+) installed in Helios 5 UX (ThermoFisher Scientific) microscope at NCBJ. Final thinning of the lamellae was performed with 5 keV Ga^+ ions followed by 2 keV Ga^+ gentle polishing. TEM observations were performed with the JEOL F200 transmission electron microscope operated at 200 kV. Since ion irradiation is depth-dependent, evaluating the damage distribution below the

sample surface induced by ion irradiation is crucial. All the lamellae were cut perpendicularly to the ion-irradiated surface to reveal the damage distribution into material up to the 2 μm depth. Afterward, images of the most degraded regions were taken to perform a detailed analysis of the defect types, size and to calculate the defect densities. The two-beam convergent beam electron diffraction technique was used to determine lamellae thickness (for dislocation density statistics) [28].

Nanoindentation was performed utilizing the Micro Materials Ltd. NanoTest Vantage system using a Synton-MDP diamond Berkovich-shaped indenter. Before starting the measurements, a Diamond Area Function (DAF) of the indenter tip was calculated using Fused Silica material in a wide load range to assess a reliable indenter shape for a given indentation depth. The hardness tests were conducted in multiple load cycles with increasing load from 0.1 mN up to 6 mN (in total 12 cycles) using load controlled method. These correspond to the depth from around 15 nm to 400 nm, depending on the irradiation fluence. Ten indentations were made at each load with 30 μm spacing between the indents. The hardness value for each material was calculated as an average value obtained from multicycle indentation.

2.3. Simulation methods

The mean projected range of the implanted Ar ions and depth distributions of defects induced by the Ar ion bombardment were estimated using Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) calculation package [11,29]. The corresponding dpa were estimated using two produced files, VACANCY.txt and NOVAC.txt under an assumed displacement energy threshold of 40 eV using the full cascade mode. The maximum damage profile estimated by SRIM is located at the depth of about 120 nm for the Ar beam energy of 380 keV.

The virtual Ni structures were created using ATOMSK software [30] and then they were transferred to MD-based LAMMPS code for further processing. Interactions between atoms were approximated by the Embedded Atom Model (EAM) potential with parameters given by Foiles [31]. To avoid surface effects, simulations were performed under periodic boundary conditions. Temperature and pressure were controlled by Nosé–Hoover algorithm [32]. The step interval was set to 1 fs. The positions of atoms were obtained after 20,000 steps, which correspond to 20 ps. The fluctuation of total energy lower than 1% was used as the indicator of the final thermalization. To obtain a structure close to the case of no thermal motion, the atomic positions over the final 250 steps of the simulation were averaged.

MC simulations were performed using the most recent versions of two simultaneously developed versions of the McChasy software, namely McChasy-1 v.65 and McChasy-2 v.2.2. In McChasy-1 [33–35], the structures are created by internal software based on crystallographic data. Thermal vibrations and desired defects are applied from built-in procedures during ongoing simulations. In McChasy-2, the structures are generated using an open-source Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator Molecular Dynamic code (LAMMPS) [36]. The potential of early versions of the code has already been presented elsewhere [37–39].

The model of edge dislocations and dislocation loops developed for McChasy-1 is based on the Peierls-Nabarro approach [40–42] and requires geometrical parameters of the defect to be determined for every structure independently [9,35,43]. To have a possibility to compare the results with part of the results previously obtained for single-phase concentrated solid-solution alloys (SP-CSAs), in this study we used the mixture of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 010 \rangle$ -oriented edge dislocations (same as in Ref. [8]).

In the McChasy-2, the $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 112 \rangle$ -oriented dislocation loops were developed along $\{111\}$ and $\{\bar{1}\bar{1}1\}$ planes. In reality, the developed defects originate as Shockley partials coming from the splitting of the $a/2 \langle 110 \rangle \{111\}$ edge dislocations [44,45]. The more detailed description of the channeling simulation procedures in both McChasy

codes (1 and 2) can be found elsewhere [8,9,34,37]. The custom software combined with Gnuplot and Open Visualization Tool (OVITO) code [46], as well as the Origin application, were used for graphical visualization.

To reveal the damage kinetics for the investigated structure, the Multi-Step Damage Accumulation (MSDA) analysis was performed [38,47]. This model is based on the equation assuming that the damage accumulation occurs through a series of structural transformations caused by the destabilization of the present crystal structure:

$$f_d = \sum_{i=1}^n (f_{d,i}^{sat} - f_{d,i-1}^{sat}) G [1 - \exp(\sigma_i(\Phi - \Phi_{i-1}))], \quad (1)$$

where: σ_i is the cross-section for the formation of a given kind of defect, $f_{d,i}^{sat}$ is the level of damage at saturation for i -th kind of defects, and Φ_i is the fluence threshold for triggering the formation of i -th kind of defects.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. TEM results

TEM analysis was performed to recognize defect types and distribution at different damage levels in investigated ion-bombarded samples. Fig. 2(a) shows cross-sectional TEM images of the samples

bombarded with Ar ions to fluences of 7×10^{14} , 7×10^{15} , and 1×10^{16} cm^{-2} . The images clearly show that in pure Ni at the lowest fluence of Ar ions, defects are evenly distributed over the depth from the surface up to deeper regions in the material, which is in line with SRIM simulations. With increasing ion fluence, defects tend to accumulate between 100 and 160 nm, and what is interesting, we do see some bubbles in contrast to the low fluences. At the highest fluence of 1×10^{16} cm^{-2} , defects migrate towards the surface and locate at a depth of 30 to 60 nm. Moreover, much bigger bubbles are formed.

In Fig. 2(b), (c), and (d), one can see that the defect size increases with the fluence, which is confirmed by performing calculations of the defect size (Fig. 2(f)) and density (Fig. 2(e)), based on the TEM images. Defect densities were calculated based on the TEM images taken at the peak damage region. For this measurement, lamellae thickness was measured at the peak damage region only. The surface area for all the materials was calculated as 1.08×10^{-13} m^2 . The densities were calculated by counting the number of defects in a unit volume of the crystalline material (volume = surface area / lamella thickness). The lamella thicknesses were as follows: 60, 108, and 65 nm, which corresponds to the fluence of 7×10^{14} , 7×10^{15} , and 1×10^{16} cm^{-2} , respectively.

One may note a slight decrease in defect density for the fluence equal to 7×10^{15} cm^{-2} . This result may be directly related to the noble gas

Fig. 2. TEM images of the Ni crystals bombarded with Ar ions to fluences of 7×10^{14} , 7×10^{15} , and 1×10^{16} cm^{-2} , denoted by Ni 7E14, Ni 7E15, and Ni 1E16, respectively: (a) cross-sectional images (orange curve represents the damage distribution profile obtained using SRIM), (b-d) bright-field images (red circles indicate dislocation loops), corresponding defect densities (e) and defect sizes (f), calculated based on the TEM images taken at the damage peak region. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

bubbles reported by TEM measurements for the mentioned fluence. The bubbles formed at the fluence of $7 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ are shown in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The reduction of defect density can be due to interactions between loops and noble gas cavities that may lead to loop punching [48], pinning, or annihilation [49,50] during the bubble growth process as a result of kinetic competition between inert gas, vacancy, and the self-interstitial atoms, especially at elevated temperatures [51]. For the higher fluence, i.e., $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the amount and size of Ar bubbles increases and argon-vacancy complexes may act as nucleation sites for the loops, and therefore the defect density increases (Fig. 2(e)). In order to quantitatively assess the number of bubbles in the structure, we calculated bubble density and their size (Fig. 3(c) and (d)). What is interesting, in the lowest fluence we observed mainly an interstitial loops and small 2–5 nm size Stacking Fault Tetrahedrons (SFT). For the intermediate ion fluence ($7 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), we additionally observe bubbles and an increase of the size of the SFTs. For the highest dose, we observe an increase in both the size of the bubbles (up to 5–10 nm) and the number of SFTs that are oriented along different crystallographic directions. It is worth noting that when a material is irradiated with gas ions, e.g., Ar^+ or He^+ , at elevated temperatures, one can expect bubbles to be visible in the structure, which may affect the mechanical properties of the material [52]. On the other hand, if it is implanted with metal ions at high temperatures, one can expect visible voids that increase with the ion fluence. Such studies are presented and described in Refs. [1,53]. For example, Lu *et al.* [53] explained that voids are the result of the three-dimensional agglomeration of vacancies, while dislocation loops and network dislocations are formed due to the agglomeration of interstitials. In this work, we postulate that the temperature-dependent increase in bubble size is due to the mobility of vacancies, Ar atoms, and clusters, which facilitate the growth of bubbles [54].

3.2. Nanomechanical results

It is well known, that in both fission and fusion materials, where the

inert gas such as He or Ar is used, a high density of nanoscale bubbles is formed [54]. These bubbles have a serious impact on the mechanical and physical properties of the material. In this work, we aim to understand the combined impact of defects formed and Ar noble gas accumulation on the hardness behavior in Ni. As shown in Fig. 4, we see that the greatest hardening for all doses occurs at a depth of 50 nm, which is consistent with the SRIM calculations, where the damage peak is located at a depth of 90–150 nm. It should be emphasized, that the plastic zone developed below the indenter tip during indentation is around five times bigger, than the given indentation depth, therefore, in order to read an

Fig. 4. Nanoindentation hardness of Ni samples irradiated up to the fluence of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. 3. (a-b) Bright-field images of bubbles in Ni bombarded samples with the fluences of $7 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, denoted by Ni 7E15 and Ni 1E16 respectively, (c) Ar bubble density, and (d) average bubble size.

appropriate hardness value, the indentation depth should be carefully chosen. It is worth mentioning, that we were unable to measure hardness at shallower depths (up to 20 nm) because surface effects interfered with correct hardness readings.

The most pronounced hardening was observed for the highest ion fluence. Interestingly, according to the TEM analysis, for the fluence $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, defects are shifted to the surface of the sample, at a depth between 30 nm and 100 nm, which could also affect the highest hardness reading in this range. For example, for NiFe irradiated with 1.5 MeV Ni^+ to fluences ranging from 4×10^{13} to $3 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (~ 0.08 – 63.5 dpa) at 150 K, coalescence and growth of small defects can substantially reduce the irradiation-induced lattice strain and mechanical stress, which can cause the retraction of defects to a shallower depth [2]. Moreover, one can see that in the most damaged structures, in which argon bubbles were formed, i.e., for the doses $7 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the hardness locally decreases successively at a depth of approximately 100–200 nm, where the highest concentration of the bubbles is present, and then increases and remains at a similar level.

Above 200 nm, the bubble concentration decreases, and the hardening rises, ultimately reaching a higher hardening level than the lowest dose of $7 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, where the number and size of defects are smaller.

3.3. RBS/C simulations and MSDA using McChasy-1

The main idea behind the chosen implantation parameters was to observe how radiation defects behave under conditions comparable to those in the HT reactor. It seems logical that due to the different mobility of defects, one should observe different defect kinetics for similar fluences implanted at low temperature (LT), RT, and HT. The results

obtained in this research are compared with the LT and RT investigations with relatively similar (except for the temperature) irradiation conditions (Ni:Ar 500 keV at 16 K and Ni:Si 550 keV at 300 K) published elsewhere [8].

RBS/C spectra collected for the Ni single crystals with different fluences of Ar ions implanted at ~ 800 K and corresponding MC simulations are shown in Fig. 5(a). As expected for materials that mainly form dislocations upon ion irradiation, no apparent damage peak (centered at about the maximum ion range) was formed. However, the dechanneling level of aligned spectra increases as a function of Ar fluence, following the damage induced inside the investigated material.

The obtained damage profiles confirm that the concentration of point defects or amorphous-like damage domains inside HT-implanted samples is low. Defect profiles are shifted into the depth of the samples (at around 200 nm), compared to the results obtained from SRIM simulations, where the damage peak is located at around 100 nm (see Fig. 5(b)). This so-called ‘long-range’ effect was already studied in several monocrystalline materials and it was shown that it is more pronounced in *fcc* than in *hcp/bcc* structures, as the stress for dislocation propagation is generally smaller in *fcc* metals [2,55]. This effect is also visible in the TEM cross-sectional images and the nanoindentation results. However, as already mentioned, also the shift toward the surface of the sample for the highest dose was observed. This is not the case for RBS/C analysis. Here, starting from the lower dose, the shape of the damage profiles is relatively similar.

Points in the MSDA graph (Fig. 5(c)) correspond to the maximal values of the extended defects profiles formed in the irradiated materials. Solid lines are the fits made using the MSDA equation. The first clear outcome of the analysis is a significantly lower level of saturation

Fig. 5. (a) Ni RBS/C spectra recorded along $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction (squares) with fits obtained using McChasy-1 simulations (solid lines of corresponding colors). Pristine and random spectra are included as references. (b) Damage distribution profiles and Ni ion range obtained from McChasy-1 simulations and SRIM calculations. (c) Damage kinetics for different bombardment conditions of Ni single crystals: full squares represent the maximal values of extended defect distributions extracted from the McChasy simulations while solid lines are the fits to the experimental data using the MSDA model; red color corresponds to the HT results described in this research while black corresponds to LT and blue to RT studies described in Ref. [8]. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

curves in samples irradiated at high temperatures when compared to RT and LT experiments. The cross-sections for the damage formation (Table 1) in the case of HT implantation are also lower compared to the RT and LT ones.

It seems that the irradiation temperature plays a significant role in the defect accumulation. This is likely an effect of the increased mobility of defects at HT that leads to more efficient annihilation. The irradiation temperature is already in the peak swelling regime [56], hence the void swelling and cluster-dislocation interactions that are observed for the higher fluence in the 5th recovery stage ($\sim 0.3 T_m$) [57] should take place. It may suggest also that most of the point defects and/or clusters formed during the implantations are annealed due to the temperature of the process. What is interesting, in the case of HT irradiation another step for the higher fluence is visible, which was observed also for SP-CSA alloys [8]. It is worthwhile to note that this step is created for the high dose (~ 25 dpa). The height of the spectrum and the additional level in The MSDA are most likely a combination of two effects. Firstly, in this regime, the growth and collapse of dislocation loops to dislocation tangles for pure metallic structures were reported [58] and secondly, this is an effect related to the agglomeration of implanted Ar in the form of bubbles visible in TEM pictures (Fig. 3).

3.4. RBS/C simulations using McChasy-2

To test how the results for more realistic finite dislocation loop models look like the experimental spectra were simulated using the McChasy-2 code. The tests were performed for pristine, random, and the most damaged (i.e. $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) experimental RBS/C spectra. Usually, a distribution of the loop sizes is observed in Ni-like *fcc* metallic structures. It seems that the general agreement is that during RT implantation, the size of the formed loops varies between 1 to 10 nm [51]. Many authors have commonly claimed that the size of the loops formed in *fcc* metals is around 3–6 nm [59,60]. This statement is somehow proved by our TEM measurements ((Fig. 2(f). For the current MD investigations, the loops were developed by removing two circle-shaped layers of atoms of a diagonal of 3, 4, and 5 nm in the middle of the pristine cell along the $\{111\}$ plane. After cutting out, the LAMMPS relaxation procedure was run for the next few ps to stabilize the system and create the targeted defects. The outcoming cells with the defects formed are shown in Fig. 6. One can observe that during the relaxation procedures, the resulting sizes of the defects (recognized as partial dislocation loops using dislocation analysis (DXA) by OVITO software) are broader than the given ones.

Next, the developed defects are cut off, multiplied, and merged for the use in the McChasy-2 code, as shown in Fig. 7(a). The code randomizes the arrangement of cubes taking into account the introduced distribution. In order to create more realistic defects (different orientations), a similar set of loops was created along the $\{\bar{1}\bar{1}1\}$ plane in the virtual sample. The distributions of the created loops used for the MC simulations combined with the results of the SRIM calculations are shown in Fig. 7(d). The experimental spectra and the simulated fits made using the second generation of the McChasy are shown in Fig. 7(c). Due to the observation of a high concentration of Ar bubbles in the implanted material, in the new version of the code we tried to investigate their impact on the RBS/C spectra. For this purpose, we developed a model of such bubbles in the investigated structure (Fig. 7(b)). In a sphere of approximately 5 nm in size, we replaced 90 % of the Ni atoms with Ar atoms and distributed them randomly inside the sphere. Since

the density of bubbles in the modified layer is comparable (or higher) to the density of defects (Fig. 2(e) and 3(c)), we distributed them homogeneously so that their density was at the level of the maximum density of defects (without taking into account the bubbles themselves – Fig. 7 (d)). To obtain a relatively smooth spectrum, the simulations were carried out for 20 samples with overall distributions presented in Fig. 7 (d).

The average loop density received from the second generation of the code was estimated from equation $\rho = \frac{D}{V}$ where V is the volume of the virtual sample and D is the average diameter of all dislocation-like defects and bubbles (same as for TEM investigations). The average loop density calculated in this way is equal to $4.86 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $2.91 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for 25 dpa without and with the bubbles considered, respectively. The value is in the range of reported experimental values [12,61]. The negligible difference regarding the absolute value of the dislocation densities, which can be observed by comparing the results obtained from the different generations of the code, is due to the different models of extended defects used for the simulations. In McChasy-2, the finite loops are placed along *diagonal* planes, which affects fewer trajectories of channeling ions compared to perpendicular, infinite edges used in McChasy-1. What should be highlighted is that the relative disorder difference between different values of dpa or fluences obtained using both generations of the code remains the same. However, the influence of the bubbles in the simulations is clearly visible. By not having the ability to simulate them in Ni in the first generation of the code, we may unjustifiably exaggerate the number of defects in the simulated distributions.

4. Conclusions

In the article, we present and discuss the recent results of the combination of several experimental and simulation techniques performed to investigate defects formed inside Ni single crystals implanted at HT with 380 keV Ar ions. The newest versions of the McChasy-1 and McChasy-2 codes were successfully implemented to quantify the number of defects and determine the depth profiles. LAMMPS combined with the McChasy-2 code was utilized to model the shape of dislocation loops (and for the latter, argon bubbles) formed inside the irradiated material.

The first outcome of the analysis performed using McChasy-1 is a low level of saturation curves due to much higher mobility of defects at HT and hence, the efficient dynamic annealing that occurs already during the implantation. The resulting distributions of the defects obtained for the real experimental spectrum are in good agreement with the SRIM code predictions. A second step in damage kinetics is visible for the highest dose (i.e., 25 dpa) as a consequence of the entanglement of dislocations and agglomeration of noble gas bubbles. The simulations performed using the second generation of the McChasy code proved that the impact of the bubbles formed inside the material is not negligible and disregarding them may exaggerate the quantitative analysis of defects in the simulated spectra. A comparison of the simulations performed using two generations of the McChasy code leads to the conclusion that the obtained shapes of the distributions are very similar. A small difference was observed regarding the absolute values of dislocation densities due to the different models of dislocations used in both codes (infinite edge dislocations for McChasy-1 oriented along channeling axis and finite loops for McChasy-2).

Nanomechanical tests revealed that in the most damaged structures, i.e., in those where the Ar bubbles were formed, the measured hardness

Table 1
Cross-sections for defect formation extracted from the MSDA model.

	$\sigma_1(10^{-14}\text{cm}^2)$	$fd_1(10^{10}\text{cm}^{-2})$	$\sigma_2(10^{-14}\text{cm}^2)$	$fd_2(10^{10}\text{cm}^{-2})$	$\Phi_2(10^{14}\text{cm}^{-2})$
Ni:Ar LT	1.3	11.1	–	–	–
Ni:Si RT	0.6	7.2	–	–	–
Ni:Ar HT	0.2	2.0	0.1	5.0	70.0

Fig. 6. Dislocation loops along $\{111\}$ plane developed using MD-LAMMPS after the relaxation. Obtained cells with loops of different sizes and corresponding top views (bottom row) of cells with defect visualizations after DXA analysis (colors corresponding to the differently oriented parts of the loops) are shown.

Fig. 7. (a) Example of an MD/McChasy-created large structure. Surrounding atoms were removed from the structure to highlight defects inside the virtual sample. The resulting dislocation loops, marked by DXA analysis, were left (inset–top view along (100) direction). (b) Same structure with homogeneously distributed Ar bubbles. (c) Experimental and simulated RBS/C spectra obtained using depth distributions of defects shown in (d).

decreases locally and successively at the depth of approximately 100–200 nm, where the highest concentration of the bubbles is present, and then increases and remains at a similar level. TEM images disclosed that, in the lowest fluence regime, mainly interstitial loops and small 2–5 nm size SFTs are present. For the intermediate ion fluence ($7 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), we additionally observe bubbles and an increase of the size of the SFTs. For the highest dose, we observe an increase in both the size of the bubbles (up to 5–10 nm) and the number of SFTs that are oriented along different crystallographic directions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

C. Mieszczynski: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **E. Wyszowska:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **P. Jozwik:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software. **K. Skrobas:** Visualization, Software, Data curation. **K. Stefanska-Skrobas:** . **M. Barlak:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **R. Ratajczak:**

Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **A. Kosinska:** Investigation. **W. Chrominski:** Investigation. **K. Lorenz:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Data availability statement

The raw/processed data required to reproduce the findings in this study cannot currently be shared as the data also forms part of several ongoing studies. However, the data may be made available from the corresponding author upon request.

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